

Innovation in Education Adapting Political Theory to the 4.0 Industrial Revolution

Tran Thi My Binh

Department of Political Theory, Tan Trao University, Tuyen Quang, Viet Nam

Suggested Citation

Binh, T.T.M. (2023). Innovation in Education Adapting Political Theory to the 4.0 Industrial Revolution. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(6), 1012-1018.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(6\).98](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(6).98)

Abstract:

The world is changing dramatically as a result of the fourth industrial revolution. To adapt to practical requirements, higher education, particularly political theory education, must adjust its aims, content, and teaching methods. If political theory lecturers in today's universities adapt well to the changes of the 4.0 industrial revolution, the role of political theory education in training high-quality human resources to meet the requirements of national development, openness, and international integration will become increasingly important.

Keywords: *fourth industrial revolution, higher education, political theory, lectures, method, challenges.*

Received: 28-10-2023

Accepted: 20-12-2023

The Fourth Industrial Revolution and the Current State of Higher Education

The world is witnessing massive and outstanding advances in science and technology as a result of the fourth industrial revolution (also known as the 4.0 industrial revolution) in the twenty-first century. This highlights once again the immense impact of science and technology on society and human existence. These broad and profound effects are having a significant impact on all aspects of the socioeconomic life of every country and nation. The 4.0 industrial revolution is defined by the widespread and effective application of technology, data science, and artificial intelligence to support industry and social life. Without a doubt, the 4.0 industrial revolution creates exceptionally advantageous conditions for people to discover new knowledge and improve the scale and quality of the economy. It presents huge opportunities,

particularly in the industrial sector, but it also represents significant obstacles, requiring countries, from strategists and policymakers to regular people, to adjust and adapt fast to new realities.

Along with the rest of the globe, the Asia-Pacific area is experiencing a strong 4.0 industrial revolution, including Vietnam, a country that is seeing rapid advancement and application of technology in production and life, as well as enormous diversity in all sectors of social life. Clearly, Vietnam has not missed the historical train of the era with the 4.0 industrial revolution. Technology is not inherently beneficial or bad; it all relies on the purpose for which society and people use and utilize technology.

Resolution of the Politburo - Central Executive Committee term XII (No. 52NQ/TW, September 27, 2019) on a number of guidelines and policies to proactively participate in the

students' skills in discovering and selecting information, as well as critical thinking skills, laying the groundwork for them to adapt to the quickly approaching 4.0 industrial revolution.

The fourth industrial revolution has also created numerous beneficial conditions for lecturers in Vietnamese universities today, particularly in the sphere of innovating modern teaching methods. To begin with, the supply of teaching materials is incredibly broad due to the expansion of the internet connection system and vast data, which allow lecturers to access numerous domestic and foreign documents, which serve well in producing lectures. They can study profoundly about teaching challenges from a variety of cognitive perspectives, expanding their own perspective on the subject and allowing them to be more confident in their teaching practice. With various modern teaching software solutions for technical means appropriate to the individual subject and target learners, instructors have several options. More crucially, the 4.0 revolution has resulted in significant changes in teaching for lecturers, with the rise of online teaching, e-learning, and so on. They can connect with and accompany pupils directly and indirectly both within and outside of class.

Aside from the good effects, the 4.0 industrial revolution is posing a number of problems, requiring lecturers to exert greater effort in their teaching duties. Many teaching assistance systems, for example, demand lecturers to continually update new learning approaches in order to avoid boredom throughout the teaching and learning process. According to research conducted by educational experts around the world, there are already more than 200 support tools available for use in the teaching and research processes. Of course, not everyone understands or can apply these skills in practice. Furthermore, port technology is growing more current, so if teachers do not stay up, it will be difficult to implement in the classroom, reducing teaching efficacy.

On the other hand, because of the "open," multidimensional, and abundant supply of materials, students may have difficulty selecting documents when studying. Not to add that there

are several unofficial and uncensored document sources on the internet, making it much more difficult to identify correct, scientific materials that have been suppressed when used. To actually become effective guides and facilitators of student learning, lecturers must regularly upgrade themselves.

Educational Innovation in Contemporary Political Theory Subjects: Opportunities and Problems

The Function of Education Higher education political theory in the fourth industrial revolution

First and first, it must be stated that, in the context of the 4.0 industrial revolution, the role of education in universities on Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh ideology has not lessened. In other respects, it's even more critical. Because humans require a scientific worldview and dialectical thinking methods as a foundation for flexible improvisation and adaptability to changing social contexts. Furthermore, with the Fourth Industrial Revolution, machines and artificial intelligence will be able to efficiently replace people in a wide range of activities, However, no machine or technological method can replace the formation, development, and improvement of personality linked with political, intellectual, moral, and lifestyle education. Marxism-Leninism remains the only ideology that aims for and clearly indicates the route to entirely liberate the world's working class, laboring people, and oppressed peoples from all epidemics, exploitation, poverty, and social injustice. Furthermore, Marxism-Leninism clearly demonstrates the route and revolutionary forces capable of accomplishing that historical destiny. Marxism-Leninism is a worldview and scientific technique that gives individuals a tool to observe and develop the reality, which is always important in human actions.

Marxism-Leninism in Vietnam is Ho Chi Minh's Thought - a comprehensive and profound system of viewpoints on the fundamental issues of the Vietnamese revolution, the result of the

creative application and development of Marxism-Leninism to the specific conditions of our country, inheriting and developing good traditional values of the nation, and absorbing the flower of human culture. Our Party has led the Vietnamese revolution from triumph to victory by using and creatively expanding Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's philosophy. It is more important than ever to confirm clearly. Marxism-Leninism considers Ho Chi Minh to be a precious provincial asset, firmly ensuring all wins of the Vietnamese revolution, especially on the path to the objective of affluent people, strong country, democracy, fairness, and civilized society. Theoretical understanding of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology must be prioritized in scientific, serious, and effective teaching and learning in order to establish a firm foundation knowledge for human resources. High quality is at the heart of today's significant innovation. That is a measurable requirement that has been validated in practice.

The actuality of our contemporary revolutionary process is fraught with complications. The development of a socialist-oriented market economy in the context of globalization and opening up to international integration that our Party and State are implementing raises a slew of new questions. We are in an era of transition in which the economy and society are inextricably linked, making it difficult to discern between them. The process of opening up integration and aggressively doing business with capitalist countries necessitates the employment of a variety of capitalist solutions and development strategies to construct socialism, providing numerous obstacles for theoretical study, particularly ideological and political work. In that attitude, scientific and creative thinking must be used to propagate and educate Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology in order to persuade future generations of students in an era of openness and deep international integration.

Improving the Quality of Political Theory Instruction in Today's University System

In the 4.0 industrial revolution, particular attention should be made to political theory education in universities and colleges to increase the quality of high-quality human resources in the future, meet the objectives of national development, and retain socialist orientation. Clearly, intellectual foundation, perspective, viewpoint on life and worldview, ethics, and lifestyle all have a significant impact on the conduct of high-quality human resources. As a result, in order to integrate into the world while keeping the features of a country developing a socialist orientation, it is required to fully innovate the teaching and learning of political theory courses at universities and colleges. Of course, within the framework of today's universal duration for university training, our country's university education must teach and learn not only specialized subjects, but also political theory subjects in order to achieve the dual goal of knowledge, "both teaching letters and teaching people." We must acknowledge that in the current training program, teaching Marxist-Leninist subjects and Ho Chi Minh's ideology faces many limitations in terms of time, program structure, quality, and teaching methods, causing a large number of students to lack motivation and interest in learning, resulting in a lack of basic theoretical knowledge.

Implementing Conclusion 94-KL/TW dated March 28, 2014 of the Secretariat on "Continuing to innovate political theory learning in the national education system", in 2019, the Ministry of Education and Training coordinated In cooperation with the Central Propaganda Department, we have completed the development of a set of programs, curriculum of 5 political theory subjects taught in universities and colleges, and starting to be taught from the 2019-2020 school year. Conclusion 94-KL/TW's content is to innovate the study of political theory in the national education system in order to generate new steps, have greater results, quality, and efficiency, and so contribute to the effectiveness of democracy. Marxism-

Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's ideology, and the Party's guidelines and viewpoints truly play a leading role in social life, ensuring that Vietnam's young generation possesses sufficient qualities and abilities, remains steadfast on the ideological foundation, and is loyal to the Party's goals and ideals and the revolutionary path that our people have chosen. The National Assessment Council has created and approved the revised political theory curriculum, which includes 5 courses and 11 details: Marxist-Leninist Philosophy: 3 credits, Marxist-Leninist Political Economy: 2 credits, Scientific Socialism: 2 credits, Communist Party of Vietnam History: 2 credits, and Ho Chi Minh's Thought: 2 credits. Overall, it is a significant and absolutely necessary change that better meets the needs of the country's higher education practice.

Innovative Political Theory Teaching Techniques in the 4.0 Industrial Revolution Period

To begin, it is vital to raise awareness that changing teaching techniques and forms in present higher education is a must in the 4.0 industrial revolution. This procedure can be challenging for each instructor at first, therefore each person must be determined and persistent in order to fulfill the teaching work in accordance with the new standards. A proactive and confident mind will be the driving force in assisting teachers to properly embrace the 4.0 industrial revolution and use its achievements into their educational operations. The job of the "traditional" teacher is changing from one of transmitting knowledge to one of organizing and guiding pupils to receive and expand knowledge. Each lecturer must constantly develop their professional capability, foreign languages, computer abilities, and new teaching methods. That is both a requirement and a considerable difficulty for today's university teachers.

Second, the need for innovation in higher education during the integration phase necessitates that lecturers be sincerely dedicated and passionate about pedagogy, have great inner strength, and be constantly creative and

innovative in their work, forming many ideas and converting them into actual activities. With the new curriculum's Political Theory courses, we can entirely choose various new teaching techniques such as group discussion; using issue situations, teaching from angles, online teaching... as well as teaching technological support tools such as edmodo, kahoot, youtube... Of course, each subject has its own set of rules. Lecturers, in particular, must select the most effective teaching methods and strategies in order to maximize efficiency while also promoting interest and active learning among students.

Third, the contemporary technology revolution necessitates that students be proactive, actively study and train themselves, and accept responsibility for all actions both inside and outside of the classroom. To adapt to the era of digital technology, data, and the internet of things, their learning techniques must also evolve. It is still vital to provide conditions for students to study and gain knowledge utilizing open, free, and creative approaches, and to be flexible and proactive in learning rather than simply memorizing to "return the lesson" in a formal style, whether it is political theory courses. With today's E-Learning system, instructors can upload whole lectures, exercises, reference materials, and particular chapter requirements for self-study and self-research. As a result, if students approach learning with a proactive and positive attitude, they will be able to master the fundamentals of the course before entering the classroom. Face-to-face classroom sessions can be transformed into open-ended sessions in which lecturers can discourse, discuss, suggest, and clarify difficulties with students rather than deliver knowledge. Complex in theory and practice, answering issues that enhance students' thinking... thereby convincing and "conquering" them of the veracity of theoretical knowledge of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology.

Fourth, the general guiding motto for higher education, including the education of political theory subjects in current universities, must be consistent with the Secretariat's conclusions on continuing to innovate political theory study in

the national education system (No. 94-KL/TW, March 28, 2014). That is, "building a team of political theory teachers who are dedicated, love their job, are absolutely loyal, have faith, and have profound, up-to-date knowledge of these subjects associated with Practice." This is a critical aspect in the continued success of innovative political theory learning in schools" (2). It is also stated that "developing human resources, particularly high-quality human resources... produces a significant, comprehensive, and fundamental change in the quality of education and training associated with recruitment and employment mechanisms." apply and treat human resources, stimulate research, transfer, application, and strong development of science and technology, innovation, and arouse the desire to establish a wealthy and happy country" (3).

Fifth, in the current setting, every university lecturer must successfully integrate the roles of teaching and scientific research, particularly with regard to the new practical challenges of politics, economy, and society that are emerging. In the activity of political education, ideology must not be one-sided, absolute, or codify the province's intrinsic theory, which is inherently scientific and revolutionary. Because Marxist-Leninist political theory is one-sided and absolute, it will lose its scientific essence and the richness of experience, causing theory to stagnate and harden. Propaganda and teaching of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology must be grounded in reality, with a focus on practical difficulties, particularly the realities of Vietnam during the reform period.

The existing teaching time for political theory subjects is plainly inadequate in comparison to the amount of basic knowledge of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh ideology that students require. As a result, we need appropriate measures to organize teaching and learning so that learners can have basic knowledge about these subjects after graduation and build a solid ideological foundation on that basis., profound scientific awareness, and the right action motto, are truly high-quality human resources of society in the 4.0 industrial revolution era. "Innovating the content and

educational program of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology meets the requirements of fundamental and comprehensive innovation in education and training, linking theory with practice, overcoming the overlap installed, closed" (4). In the legacy of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology, we must choose basic scientific knowledge with profound theoretical knowledge, vivid and practical practicality, methodological precision, lawfulness, and specificity... and incorporate it into the curriculum accordingly. To overcome the limitation of formal teaching time for political theory subjects, university and college training institutions must collaborate in organizing online learning and research forums for students to exchange and discuss political theoretical issues related to domestic and foreign practice, thereby deepening their political theoretical knowledge. For political theory to establish a firm intellectual foundation for each member of society's high-quality human resources, we must foster positivity and initiative in learners; organize emulation movements to learn political theory among students and practitioners.

Conclusion

The 4.0 industrial revolution is having a significant impact on many sectors of social life, particularly teaching and learning activities in universities. In the face of these opportunities and challenges, university lecturers, notably political theory lecturers, must exercise political bravery and be creative and innovative in their teaching techniques more than ever.

The most visible impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution is the introduction of robots, which can replace humans in terms of computation, memory, analysis, and high labor efficiency but cannot replace humans in moral education and personality creation and growth. High-quality human resources, inventive thinking, and a strong moral basis are all required, as are patriotism, educated civic consciousness, and social responsibility. As a result, the importance of political theory education has not lessened, but rather continues to play an important part in

the process of training human resources in the coming years - the students who are studying today. To adapt to the 4.0 industrial revolution, the existing political theory faculty must make exceptional efforts, "elevate" themselves in all aspects, and contribute significantly to educating generations of students who actually deserve to be excellent human resources. "Global citizens" are active, creative individuals who are driving our country's 4.0 industrial revolution.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by Tan Trao University in Tuyen Quang, Viet Nam.

References

Communist Party of Vietnam Electronic Bao. (2021). Resolution of the Politburo - Central Executive Committee term XII (No. 52-NQ/TW, September 27, 2019) on a variety of

policy issues and vigorous engagement in the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Electronic Bao of the Communist Party of Vietnam. (2014). Secretariat Conclusion on Continuing to Innovate Political Theory Learning in the National Education System (No. 94-KL/TW, March 28, 2014).

Communist Party of Vietnam Electronic Bao. (2021). Full text of the Party's 13th National Congress Resolution.

Tran Khanh Duc. (2014). Education and human resource development in the 21st century. Vietnam Education Publishing House.

Vu, J. (2016). *Education in the age of knowledge*. Labor Publishing House.

Bao, D.Q. & Phuong, L.T. (2017). Building a learning society in the era of the fourth industrial revolution. *Education Magazine*, 412, 1-3.

Thanh, P.C. (2018). Industrial Revolution 4.0 - the development trend of online education. *Education Magazine*, 421, 43-46.